

A Rare Disease, Spinal Tuberculosis-First Case Report from Lahore, Pakistan

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Abstract

Spinal tuberculosis is the tuberculosis of the spine presented as the extra pulmonary tuberculosis. It is chronic and destructive form of Tb which slowly progress and often leads to severe complications like paralysis, destruction of intervertebral disc, kyphosis or gibbus formation. It is rarely encountered that leads to its misdiagnosis. Furthermore the most prevalent symptom for spinal of spinal tuberculosis is lower back pain. We report a 50 year old male case, with a history of 4 year persistent lower back and 2 months of leg pain along with weakness. When he

was presented to the hospital he was febrile with temperature of 38C. He was weak, couldn't walk without support and had weight loss during the past few months. Rapid diagnosis must be done for appropriate implementation of treatment. Along with physical examination CBC, ESR, DLC tests were done for proper diagnosis of disease. Further tests confirmed the spinal tuberculosis. Upon proper diagnosis the conservative treatment of patient was started. But the doctor also recommended surgical treatment for speedy recovery of patient. After the successful surgery the patient health was improved greatly. Anti-tuberculosis drugs regimen was followed during the stay in the hospital. As a result the patient health was recovered speedily after the appropriate

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treatment. Soon after the treatment the patient was able to walk again on his two feet without support.

BACKGROUND

Spinal tuberculosis (ST) refers to the tuberculosis of spine. ST is one of the ancient diseases of mankind that has been found in Egyptian mummies [1]. Sir Percival Potts first devised the name of the disease in 1779 [2]. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* was discovered to be the causative agent of spinal tuberculosis [3]. ST accounts 50% of osseous tuberculosis and not commonly observed like fundamental tuberculosis causing infection of pulmonary or lungs. The graph of spinal tuberculosis cases increases gradually day by day in both endemic and developed countries [4]. The prevalence of spinal tuberculosis is not exactly figured out in most regions of the globe. It is generally present commonly in endemic countries among young adults and children. It is less common in western world and affecting mostly the adult population in western and Middle East territories [2]. In 2016, 10.4 million new tuberculosis cases reported as per WHO. European regions contributed 3%, South-East Asian regions 46.5% and India alone consider 23% burden of Tb worldwide [5].

THE CASE

A 50 years old male presented to the neurosurgery department of a tertiary level hospital had been referred from a private clinic, with a 4 years persistent L.B.P (lower back pain), 2 months of leg pain and gait was not steady. He was also found to have high fever, cough and weight loss. The patient health was stable when he had lower back pain which was treated locally and analyzed during the 4 year period. Furthermore, 2 months back patient had lower limb pain with difficulty in ambulating. Later on, the patient did not walk properly without support.

Upon admission to the hospital, the patient was wide awake and alert in obvious discomfort. He was febrile with temperature of 38°C. Heart Rate (HR),

blood pressure (BP) and respiratory rate (RR) were as follows: HR: 81 beats per minute, BP: 120/70mmHg, and RR: 18 breaths per minute. In the last few months he had weight loss. Initial laboratory examination revealed: Hemoglobin: 15.9 g/dL (normal range: 11.5-16 g/dL), RBC count: $5.53 \times 10^{12}/L$ (normal range: $4.00 - 6.0 \times 10^{12}/L$), HCT: 45.7% (normal range: 35-60 %), MCV: 82.6 fL (normal range: 80.0 - 99.0 fL), MCH: 28.7 pg (normal range: 27.0 – 31.0 pg), MCHC: 34.7 g/dL (normal range: 33.0 – 37.0 g/dL), Platelet Count: $194 \times 10^9/L$ (normal range: 150 – 450 $\times 10^9/L$), TLC: $6.36 \times 10^9/L$ (normal range: $4.5 - 10.5 \times 10^9/L$), ESR: 12 mm/hr (normal range: 1–13 mm/hr) (table 1 & 4). A laboratory test for differential leukocyte count (DLC) was also done. Upon special investigation X-ray of abdomen was done. The results of DLC and X-ray revealed that everything was in normal range (table 2). The patient was diagnosed with spinal tuberculosis. His treatment was started with NSAIDS (Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs). Rifampin 150mg, isoniazid 75 mg, ethambutol HCL 275 mg and Pyrazinamide 400mg, has been given to the patient 4 tablets per day for treating tuberculosis. His drug regimen was given in table 3.

TABLE 1: CBC AND DLC

Complete Blood Count (CBC)	Lab reports	Normal Values
Hemoglobin (Hb)	15.9 g/dL	11.5 – 16 g/dL
RBC Count	$5.53 \times 10^{12}/L$	$4.00-6.00 \times 10^{12}/L$
HCT	45.7 %	35-60 %
MCV	82.6 fL	80.0 - 99.0 fL
MCH	28.7 pg	27.0 – 31.0 pg
MCHC	34.7 g/dL	33.0 – 37.0 g/dL
Platelet Count	$194 \times 10^9/L$	150 – 450 $\times 10^9/L$
Differential Leukocyte Count (DLC)		
Neutrophils	58 %	50-70 %

Lymphocytes	37 %	20-45 %
Monocytes	03 %	02-08 %
Eosinophils	02 %	01-04 %

TABLE 2: X-RAY ABDOMEN

X-ray	Lab report
Abdomen	
Liver	Liver is 17.5 in size and altered texture. No focal lesion seen. CBD and portal vein are normal. No intra/ extra hepatic biliary dilatation.
Gall Bladder	It is normal. Partially contracted.
Pancreas	Normal size. Homogeneous parenchyma. No focal lesion. Duct is not dilated.
Spleen	Normal size (14cm). No focal lesions.
Both Kidneys	Both kidneys are normal in size and show parenchymal echogenicity with preserved CM differentiation. No calculi, mass or hydro nephrosis on either side.
Urinary Bladder	No abscess/ ascites, no enlarged lymph nodes.
Impression	Normal abdomen ultrasound

TABLE 3: REGIMEN OF DRUGS FOLLOWED DURING THE STAY IN HOSPITAL. PRESCRIBED DRUGS, DOSAGE, USAGE DURATION AND USAGE DAYS.

Drug	Dosage	Usage duration	Usage days
Rifampin 150mg	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance
Isoniazid 75 mg	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance
Ethambutol HCL 275 mg	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance
Pyrazinamide 400mg	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance
Vitamin B6	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance

Piroxicam 20 mg	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance
Pregabalin 50 mg	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance
Chlorzoxazone	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance
Diclofenac	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance
Paracetamol	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance
Pantoprazole	1 tablet/day	1 month	After admittance

TABLE 4: AB INVESTIGATION SHEET

AB Investigation Flow Sheet

Tests	Lab Reports	Normal Values
Hemoglobin (Hb)	15.1 g/dL	11.5 – 16 g/dL
WBC	7.7 x10 ⁹ /L	4.5 to 11.0 x10 ⁹ /L
Platelets	253 x10 ⁹ /L	150 – 450 x10 ⁹ /L
S. Urea	30 mg/dL	5 to 20 mg/dL
S. Cr	0.9 mg/dL	0.7 to 1.3 mg/dL
Bil	0.9 mg/dL	0.1 to 1.2 mg/dL
ALT	24 U/L	4 to 36 U/L
AST	34 U/L	8 to 33 U/L
ALK PO ₄	204 IU/L	30 to 120 IU/L
PT	15 seconds	11 to 13.5 seconds
APTT	32 seconds	25 to 35 seconds
INR	1.0	1.1 or below
Albumin	3.7 g/dL	3.4 to 5.4 g/dL

DISCUSSION

Spinal Tuberculosis (ST) is a chronic and destructive form of Tb which slowly progress and often leads to severe complications like neurological injury (paralysis), destruction of intervertebral disc, kyphosis (Severe curve in vertebrae) or gibbus formation (small curve in vertebrae) because of its insidious diagnosis [6]. This disease is mostly prevalent in developing countries [2]. Spinal involvement in caries spine is generally a consequence of

hematogenous dissemination of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* into the thick vascular system of cancellous bone of the vertebrae. The first infection site includes mainly either genitourinary system infection or pulmonary lesion. Paraplegia (it refers to loss of sensory activities probably in the lower extremities which means paralysis of both legs) is the most destructive complications of spinal Tb [7]. So, its early diagnosis and treatment must be done to avoid serious complications [8]. X-ray, MRI, CT scan all are crucial tests for diagnosis of spinal tuberculosis [9].

A case study was reported in which a 45 year old male was presented to the hospital with symptoms of LBP (lower back pain), body aches, intermittent hyperpyrexia, inflammation in right flank, lower right limb weakness and sweating [10]. This case study was in line with our patient case study as our 50 year old male patient had a history of 4 year persistent lower back and 2 months of leg pain and weakness. When he was presented to the hospital he was febrile with temperature of 38°C. He was weak, couldn't walk without support and had weight loss during the past few months.

Spinal tuberculosis is highly rare that can lead to misdiagnosis because it is insidious and non-specific. Different laboratory tests must be done for precise diagnosis of spinal tuberculosis. Complete blood count (CBC), C-reactive protein (CRP), parathyroid hormone, erythrocyte sedimentation test (ESR), creatinine, electrolyte, alkaline phosphatase, alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase and PPD tests must be performed for proper diagnosis of spinal tuberculosis. Also X-ray and CT scan play vital role in detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [11]. In this present study laboratory evaluation was done for proper diagnosis. Test results were Hemoglobin: 15.9 g/dL (normal range: 11.5-16 g/dL), RBC count: $5.53 \times 10^{12}/L$ (normal range: $4.00 - 6.0 \times 10^{12}/L$), HCT: 45.7% (normal range: 35-60 %), MCV: 82.6 fL (normal range: 80.0 - 99.0 fL), MCH: 28.7 pg (normal range: 27.0 - 31.0 pg), MCHC: 34.7 g/dL (normal range: 33.0 - 37.0 g/dL), Platelet Count: $194 \times 10^9/L$

(normal range: 150 – 450 $\times 10^9/L$), TLC: 6.36 $\times 10^9/L$ (normal range: 4.5 – 10.5 $\times 10^9/L$), ESR: 12 mm/hr (normal range: 1-13 mm/hr). A laboratory test for differential leukocyte count (DLC) was also done (Table 1 & 4). Upon special investigation X-ray of abdomen was done. The tests results revealed that everything was normal (Table 2) than what could be the reason that cause our patient severe lower back and leg pain. Further investigation was done to rule out this problem. The investigation led to the diagnosis of spinal tuberculosis.

Spinal tuberculosis treatment can be surgical, conservative or both. After proper diagnosis of spinal tuberculosis doctors prescribed the anti TB drugs to the patients for 6 to 9 months. Along with anti TB drugs operative treatment is also done to prevent the disease progression [12]. Dean et al. in 2019 reported a case study in which a 26 year old male prisoner was diagnosed with spinal tuberculosis. This patient case was complicated and doctors underwent T6-7 hemilaminectomy. The surgery was successful and after the surgery the patient was started with anti-tuberculosis drugs to ensure his full recovery. On the day of discharge patient health was highly improved [13]. In January 2005 to January 2013 a retrospective study was conducted by Zheng et al. On 740 adult patients diagnosed with spinal tuberculosis. All patients were treated conservatively. After the conservative treatment was started 89 out of 740 patients were selected for chemotherapy. Standard chemotherapy treatment was done for 18 months and followed up for at least 2 years. The patients responded well to the chemotherapy and their health was definitely improved [14].

In case of our patient the doctor recommended both conservative and surgical treatment. Anti TB drugs were given to the patient during his stay in the hospital. Rifampin 150mg, isoniazid 75 mg, ethambutol HCL 275 mg and Pyrazinamide 400mg, has been given to the patient 4 tablets per day for treating tuberculosis. Vitamin B6 one per day has been given to the patient to

prevent numbing and tingling of the hands and feet caused by isoniazid and other Tb medicines. Piroxicam 20 mg an anti-inflammatory and anti-pain drug given per day to relieve pain of joints. Pregabalin 50 mg one per day to relieve nerve pains. Chlorzoxazone, Diclofenac, Paracetamol one per day to relax muscles. Pantoprazole one per day given for maintaining gut acidity caused by combination of drugs. These drugs have been given to the patients for at least one month, periodically (Table 3). Subsequently, after one month as the patient still complaining lower back pain. The doctor's then, prescribed a surgical treatment. Onwards, the surgery has been carried out. The outcome of surgery was positive in accordance to the target as it permits patient to walk on their own feet. But the low doses of anti-Tb and nerve relief drugs still has been taken by patient for at least 6-months in the forward visits to getting rid of every little complication.

CONCLUSION

Spinal tuberculosis is a rare condition that must be diagnosed properly to avoid severe neurological complications. It can mimic other diseases like neoplasia. One of the main symptoms presented by patients is lower back pain that is why its misdiagnosis is highly common. Differential diagnosis must be done for detection of this disease and after proper diagnosis implementation of appropriate treatment either conservative, surgical or both should be done to rule out this disease. Proper surgical and chemotherapeutic treatment will ultimately lead to the cure of spinal tuberculosis.

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